

IMPLEMENTING THE FLIPPED CLASSROOM TECHNIQUE WITH ELEMENTARY-LEVEL LEARNERS AND DETERMINING ITS EFFICACY IN IMPROVING THEIR SPEAKING ABILITIES.

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INTRODUCTION

In education, teaching is always equal to art, and the current educational world is focused on the integration of technology and the promotion of students autonomous teaching and learning approaches. Unlike the traditional way of teaching, the majority of educational organizations and teachers have already adapted to utilize the flipped classroom approach during the lesson's conduction due to its several advantages. This pedagogical approach provides an alteration of group activeness into individual performance, and in-class learning exposure is replaced with outside, self-learning comprehension of the previously shared materials. The procedure of this approach is based on Bloom's taxonomy, and the learners' attendance is characterized in accordance with Bloom's received verbs. The learners are free to explore, analyze, practice, and apply the given new concept in any way to develop their comprehension skills outside of the classroom. Out class enhanced understanding capabilities assist the learners' activeness further in class activities such as problem solving, critical thinking, analysis, and synthesis. On the other hand, according to Ranjan (2022), the flipped classroom approach is modified as the most convenient and technological one for exploring amazing tools during the lesson in order to create curious study environments. Also, he claimed that the way of teaching with the help of this approach provides opportunities to integrate the teaching process and ensures the learning outcomes of the lesson.

Even though the identified efficiency of the approach had been highlighted among many researchers, still Sonmez (2020) disputes that its findings in the area of productive skills are not enough, and he suggests further studying in this sphere. Due to this suggestion, this work is aimed at estimating the effectiveness of the flipped classroom approach for integrating speaking skills among elementary-level students.

Background

Some decades ago, among many educational places, the teaching process was mostly conducted in a didactic way, where the students were fully dependent on their teachers, and TTT (teacher talk time) was important. On the other hand, a flipped classroom approach had been adapted into education in the late 1990s by Dr. Erik Mazur, who is well known for his peer instruction. According to Gapolan, Daughrity, and Hackmann (2022) flipped learning is considered more student-centered, and this approach encourages students to review the content of a new concept as the first step in their own learning, and the teacher becomes a facilitator for

guiding the learners to apply and analyze the new concept. Shooli, Esfahani, and Sepehri (2022) advocate the view that flipped classroom approaches can assist students in finding out their study weaknesses and overcoming them by building classroom interaction. In addition, researchers emphasize the idea that the classroom environment becomes more interactive for

the students whenever they comprehend the explanations of new linguistic perspectives during the lesson due to their preparation beforehand. Being aware of their weaknesses, trying to solve their academic problems, and working on upcoming issues beforehand are all special features of the flipped classroom approach, which leads to effective learning.

On the other hand, motivation is considered an important factor in any academic achievement, and it is defined differently by different researchers. Elliott and Covington (2001) indicate motivation as a motive that makes the learners take action towards their desires and needs (cited in Alizadeh, 2016). When it comes to motivation for learning languages, Gardner (1985) illustrates that motivation is the combination of many pluses, such as endeavoring, desiring, and having a favorable attitude towards learning a foreign language (cited in Alizadeh, 2016). In addition to motivating a favorable attitude toward learning, the flipped classroom approach can also motivate learners to achieve higher academic results. The flipped classroom approach applies the usage of advanced technologies into the class, and the classes are mostly designed based on videos. Moreover, Zainuddin and Perera (2019) advocate the idea that students' intrinsic motivation towards learning can be enhanced due to the positive impact of flipped learning.

Teaching any foreign language should not only include either perceptive skills or grammar-based explanation, but the process also has to be somehow productive where students' active participation is encouraged by the facilitators. Golkovaa and Hubackovabto (2014) advocate the idea that both language productive and receptive skills are highly correlated with each other. One cannot exist separately from another as long as receptive skills play a fundamental role in productive skills. Unless the learners are good at receptive skills or passively participate in reading, listening, or grammar task-based activities, desired outcomes or goals in terms of productive skills cannot be reached.

Productive skills, both writing and speaking, are considered essential to academic success and achievement; however, speaking is more frequently used than writing. Communication is estimated as an inseparable part of human life, as people have to use the language in every step of their lives, whether it is a foreign or native one. Also, the highest results in L2 will be clearly visible whenever the learners are capable of communicating efficiently on their second language, either by explaining their ideas clearly to the audience or comprehending the ideas that were mentioned by others. Lesáková (2008) mentions that the main purpose of creating a speaking-engaged atmosphere and improving the learners speaking skills is to provide the learners with the opportunity to avoid making mistakes while communicating and work on their weaknesses, such as misspellings, faulty vocabulary, and incorrect grammar.

Among the integrated skills, speaking is estimated as an output of the language that demands a long time to adopt and produce; for that reason, speaking is considered the most challenging capability for the majority of the learners. Due to the difficulties, mostly lower-level students struggle with improving their speaking skills, which results in losing interest and confidence. Santhanasamy and Yunus (2022) identify that typically, L2 learners are demotivated by their poor speaking performance while expressing their ideas. It is difficult for them to reveal their ideas, as they do not have a wide range of vocabulary and they make pronunciation mistakes. Further research suggests the implementation of the flipped classroom approach with passive students in order to motivate them to be active inside and outside of the classroom. In addition, it should be mentioned that using the flipped approach in the class provides the chance to involve the higher cognitive level of Bloom's taxonomy

because, unlike traditional classes, the learners are autonomous during the analyzing, evaluating, and working on the before-sent video-based materials and access the learning materials by themselves. On the other hand, Sargent and Casey (2020) suggest that the flipped classroom approach has to be fundamentally facilitated with active learning for better results. Learning outcomes of the classroom approach will be seen whenever the students watch the lesson video outside of class and discuss its content during active learning in a group or a pair, and here effective application of the flipped classroom approach can be recognized by the active participation of the inspired students. (cited in Santhanasamy and Yunus, 2022)

Thus, this study is interested in implementing a "flipped classroom" approach into the lesson to improve elementary-level students speaking skills.

Research question

How does the flipped classroom approach improve elementary learners speaking skills?

Significance of the study

Among the works that have been done in the sphere of the flipped classroom approach, it is highly available to find out needed information or results about only the higher-level students. However, the effectiveness of this approach has not been measured yet among the young learners, and the integration of flipped classroom learning in the young learners' development of productive skills is highly recommended.

The study will explore the assistance of the flipped classroom approach to enhance the A2 level students speaking skills.

Definition of terms

Flipped classroom approach – is a way of active learning; it is structured in such a way that students encounter the idea of the lecture or new theme before class time in order to free up class time for activities

Lecture method- this method is considered the oldest but one of the best methods of teaching and is estimated to be a very convenient strategy to deliver a large amount of material. In this method, teacher talk time is important while students play the role of listeners.

Conceptual framework – the concept is used to identify relations between ideas and research that include one or more formal theories, findings, and other concepts as well.

Ethical consideration -is about avoiding harming any human being's rights.

Gamification - is an interactive way of teaching based on the implementation of digital tools in the classroom in order to create an engaging environment and increase collaborative skills in which students are motivated.

References:

- 1.Amri, Z. (2013). CLASSROOM ACTION RESEARCH AND LESSON STUDY: HOW DO THEY WORK FOR LECTURERS AND HIGH SCHOOL ENGLISH TEACHERS. SELT 2013 Proceeding,. Available from file:///Users/air/Downloads/6797-13530-1-SM.pdf [Accessed 20 April 2023].
- 2.Arnold, B.J.A. (2014). Gamification in Education. Research gate. Available from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/295401531_Gamification_in_Education [Accessed 19 April 2023].

3. Barghani, Z.S. (2020). The Benefits of Gamification in Learning. IJARIE. Available from http://ijarie.com/AdminUploadPdf/The_Benefits_of_Gamification_in_Learning_ijarie11788.pdf [Accessed 20 April 2023].
4. Berry, T. (2011). Pre-Test Assessment. American Journal of Business Education (AJBE), 1 (1), 19. Available from <https://doi.org/10.19030/ajbe.v1i1.4633> [Accessed 20 April 2023].
5. Bhat, A. (2019). Data Analysis in Research: Types & Methods. QuestionPro. Available from <https://www.questionpro.com/blog/data-analysis-in-research/#:~:text=For%20sure%2C%20statistical%20techniques%20are> [Accessed 20 April 2023].

